

Environmental Management Systems Best Practices

Implementation Manual

With the Financial Support of

Regional Programme for the Sustainable Management of the Coastal Zones of the Countries of the Indian Ocean (ReCoMaP)

The coastal zone is an area typically rich in natural resources and economic opportunities, including marine fisheries, mariculture, mangrove forests, tourism development, and transportation. In the Western Indian Ocean an estimated 35 million people live in the coastal zone and many of their local and national economies are sustained by these resources and opportunities.

However, the rate of exploitation of coastal resources is unsustainable. Coupled with the increasingly significant impacts of watershed deforestation, pollution, urban and tourism development, as well as global climate change, the future productivity of the coastal zone, and associated livelihoods, is seriously threatened.

ReCoMaP, a 5-year regional programme of the Indian Ocean Commission and the EU, was designed to provide support to national institutions, NGOs and civil society to achieve long-term sustainable coastal zone management and development. Operational from 2006 to 2011 in seven countries of the Indian Ocean (Comoros, Kenya, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles, Somalia and Tanzania), the Programme provides a range of support mechanisms. These mechanisms include technical assistance, financial support and training opportunities. The Programme also supports wider government-led initiatives to develop institutions (and plans) to implement a key management approach known as Integrated Coastal Zone Management (or ICZM).

One particularly significant element of ReCoMaP is the grant scheme available to NGOs, community-based organisations, and local and village governments (known collectively as non-state actors). These grants, of up to €100,000 for each beneficiary, provide an important opportunity for non-state actors to be directly involved in creating conditions for the sustainable use of coastal resources and the sustainable development of the coastal zone.

Empretec Mauritius (EM) was a partner, with the Mauritian Association des Hotels de Charme (AHC), in the original development of this important Manual on best practices related to environmental management for small and medium-sized hotels. EM was subsequently awarded a grant under the 2nd phase of ReCoMaP's non-state actor scheme to promote the uptake of this Manual across the WIO region. Working with a number of tourism development organisations from Madagascar, Seychelles and Tanzania, including Chambers of Commerce and federations of hotel owners, EM have reinforced the environmental management capacities of these organisations. Translations of the Manual have been delivered to Francophone partners and a series of sensitization events and awareness workshops have been undertaken.

ReCoMaP and the IOC would like to congratulate Empretec Mauritius, AHC and their partners for developing and subsequently widely disseminating this practical and hands-on tool for hotel managers and other tourism professionals that will contribute to reducing the environmental footprint of coastal tourism and therefore promote sustainable development of the coastal zone.

Callixte D'Offray
Secretary General
Indian Ocean Commission

Empretec is an integrated capacity-building programme, operating with the guidance of **UNCTAD**, to support promising entrepreneurs to build innovative and internationally competitive small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs), thereby contributing to the development of a dynamic private sector.

Since its inception in 1988, the Empretec programme has been initiated in 36 countries and has assisted more than 230,000 entrepreneurs through local market-driven business support Centres. In Africa, there are currently 16 centres operating, providing valuable entrepreneurship promotion and business development services to local entrepreneurs and local communities.

The **Empretec Mauritius (EM)** project was set up in 2000 and was structured as a virtual organisation, with a secretariat, and was supported and implemented by a consortium of key stakeholders, under a cooperation agreement with UNDP / Enterprise Africa. Today, Empretec Mauritius is a non-government member based agency, grouping Professionals, Managers, Entrepreneurs and other high net worth individuals from various spheres of activities operating in Mauritius and the East African Region. Their only objective is to give something back to society and support the entrepreneurial empowerments. Though Empretec Mauritius is now completely autonomous and self financing, its initial objectives, mission and vision have remained unchanged and its core activities and services can be classified as follows:

- o Enterprise Development & Capacity Building
- o Business Development & Value Added Services
- o Trade, Investment Facilitation & Regional Integration
- o Knowledge, Innovation & Corporate Social Responsibility

This project is part of the extended array of value added services that EM is currently offering with the major concern that our environment has a limit and now is the time to act. EM partnered with the Association des Hotels de Charme in 2009 to implement the EMS Best Practices Implementation project in Small and Medium Hotels in Mauritius. In the same endeavor and more expertise acquired EM embarked in a more ambitious and challenging implementation of EMS Best Practices at a regional level involving a larger number of Hotels in Mauritius, Madagascar, Seychelles and the Tanzania.

The second phase consists of implementing EMS Best Practices in a wider array of hotels ranging from small establishments to larger ones based on the Do It Yourself

principle. We are aiming by the medium to long term initiate the concept of sustainable management of the coastal zones among tourism related establishments and staff. To Ensure Maximum impact and successful implementation Empretec Mauritius has gathered a small part of its network into the implementation of this project. Some of the organizations are long time partners while others are first time collaborations. We look forward for a long term and fruitful collaboration among the partners. The latter are

1. Association des Hôtels de Charme (AHC) - Mauritius
2. Association of Inbound Operators Mauritius - Mauritius
3. "Federation des Hoteliers and Restaurateurs, Madagascar" (FHORM) - Madagascar
4. Nature Seychelles - Seychelles
5. Chambre de Commerce et d'industrie Antalaha - Madagascar
6. Chambre de Commerce et d'industrie Antsiranana - Madagascar
7. Chambre de Commerce et d'industrie Mahajunga - Madagascar
8. Chambre de Commerce et d'industrie Nosy Be - Madagascar

We also feel privileged for the assistance and support provided by ReCoMaP, the IOC and the European Delegation in Mauritius and we are indeed thankful.

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FOREWORD

The tourism product in Mauritius, Seychelles, Madagascar and Tanzania is largely dependent on the natural resource base; that is, on the physical environment. The traditional marketing approach of selling "sand, sea, and sun" has created a mind-set that has resulted in the concentration of tourist facilities in the coastal areas. Coupled with the increasing dependence of the economies on tourism earnings, the agglomeration of coastal hotels emerged as a sector of the economy, making the greatest use of coastal and marine resources. This dependency is not without cost, to both the economy and the industry. The tourism industry has undoubtedly contributed to the degradation of the coastal and marine environments. However and in particular larger coastal hotel groups, being conscious of the negative impact they have on the coastal zones have, in the past years, identified and implemented environmental best practices individually. This has not been possible for small and medium hotels and other tourism related business due to constraints linked to size, financial means and know-how. However recently there has been a joint effort by small and medium coastal hotels in Mauritius to identify and implement EMS best practices for sustainable coastal tourism.

The Manual is a reprint of the original version published in the context of the project lead by the "Association des Hotels de Charme" entitled "Implementing Environmental friendly Best Practices in Small & Medium Hotels" with the technical and financial support of the ReCoMaP. This manual will be used in the project "Implementing Environment Friendly Best practices in Coastal Zones of the Indian Ocean (With particular emphasis on Hotels, Restaurants, Aquaculture, Fisheries and other Coastal Based businesses)" supported and funded by the ReCoMaP as a continuation of the above mentioned one targeting a larger span of the tourism industry in Mauritius, Madagascar, Seychelles and Tanzania.

Madagascar (North Region), Mauritius, Seychelles and Tanzania are holiday destinations for beach-resort tourists. They possess a wide range of natural attractions; enjoy a sub-tropical climate with clear warm sea waters, attractive beaches, tropical fauna and flora complemented by a multi-ethnic and cultural population that is friendly and welcoming. These tourism assets are, their main strength, especially if they are backed up by well-designed and run hotels, and reliable and operational services and infrastructures.

The tourist industry shares a close link and is highly dependent on coastal and marine resources. It must therefore, for its sustainability, be at the forefront of actions directed towards the protection and preservation of coastal zones including marine biodiversity. However, the fragile and interconnected ecosystems in our coastal areas are experiencing increased stress due to anthropogenic activities such as, over fishing in the lagoon, pollution, erosion, overuse of coastal waters and reefs, resources mining, etc.

The survival of the tourism industry in the long term requires that all concerned (hoteliers, private sector, Institutions, NGOs, Authorities, Operators in the Tourism & Hospitality, the public and coastal communities) take the required actions for sustainable utilization of our natural resources so that the population and economy of partner countries may continue to benefit from this important sector.

Through the present project and with the technical and financial support of the ReCoMaP, the partners Empretec Mauritius, AHC, AIOM, FHORM, CCI Antalaha, CCI Antsiranana, CCI Mahajunga, CCI Nosy Be, TCCIA, TCCIA Tanga and Nature Seychelles have set the following

objectives which they consider as the first steps moving towards gaining certification for "Environmentally Friendly Hotel" label:

Objectives of the Action

- To contribute towards the reduction of the negative impacts of coastal business activities on the coastal and marine environment through the dissemination of experience and know-how on Environment Management Systems (EMS) best practices
- To contribute towards poverty alleviation through the integration of environment friendly businesses and promotion of eco tourism

The conception of this manual had been a very enriching experience and is based on the findings of environmental audits carried out in small and medium hotels across Mauritius. It reflects the hotels functional capabilities and operational realities. The Do-It-Yourself principle adopted will in a sustainable manner motivate the implementation in all the hotels of the association and in the long term all the hotels of Mauritius. The manual covers 5 main parts covering basic environmental concepts, an introduction to Environmental Management systems, documentation of an EMS policy manual and Recommendations that can be implemented on a Do It Yourself principle. The conception is based on easy to follow steps and user friendly concept.

Conception of the manual was done by:

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- Board Members of the Association Des Hotels Charme who have helped Empretec Mauritius in the conception.

We wish also to thank all our partners for their collaboration and support in the implementation of the project.

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I Introduction to Environmental Concepts

I.1 Water

Water as a nature's gift is the most abundant component on the surface of earth. It exists in a more or less pure form, made up of rain, fountains, rivers, and seas. It is a constituent part of all living organisms, and appears in natural compounds. Every ocean, river, and lake has its own specially adapted flora and fauna. That is why most marine organisms cannot live in fresh water; just as fresh water beings would be unable to live in a marine environment. On our planet, the sea is the resource holding the most biodiversity, from simple unicellular organisms to giant whales.

Tapping water resources for different activities, such as energy generation, agriculture, human consumption, and industry, among others, puts pressure on water availability and quality. Throughout this century, global water demand has increased seven-fold, whereas global population has tripled. Currently, the future of water reserves depends on the use we make of this fragile and limited resource.

All living creatures need fresh water and without it, the earth would be a lifeless planet. Water is found in rivers, lakes, lagoons, ground sources, and the atmosphere. Unfortunately, compared to our world size, and considering how essential it is to life, we actually have very little fresh water available: less than 1% of our planet's total water is liquid fresh water. We should therefore be very much careful about its use.

Efficient water use is one of the easiest best practices to implement, not only through facilities design features but also through proper management. Water-saving measures can be taken virtually in all areas of water consumption. Water-consuming areas in tourist facilities include:

- Showers, toilets, and lavatories in public bathrooms, guest rooms, and staff accommodations. Obviously, if guest rooms feature a bathtub or a jacuzzi, water consumption will be much higher.
- Laundry rooms.
- Kitchens, including rooms for food preparation and cleaning.
- General services, such as swimming pools.
- Cleaning and maintaining facilities and landscaped areas.

Practical Tips

- A company's good water use performance relies on carrying out periodic checks and keeping records that allows the identification of high consumption areas. Moreover, good recordkeeping enables you to find out whether your policies and actions are effective. Therefore you should keep a log that records the basic information appearing on the utility bill.
- If you can afford it, install meters in each operating area (kitchen, laundry room, guest rooms, etc.). In the event that you cannot do this now, make it one of your future goals. In this way, you will know which areas are generating the highest expenses and take specific water saving measures, which will also make it easier to locate leaks and carry out maintenance tasks.
- Reuse laundry wastewater in facilities cleaning tasks, such as washing walls, etc.
- Do laundry only when you have full washing machine loads, and if possible, acquire low water and energy-consumption washing machines.
- If you have landscaped areas requiring watering, leave these tasks for the afternoon or evening in order to prevent water being wasted through evaporation.
- Use sprinkler or drip irrigation systems for watering if at all possible.
- In sites where conditions allow it, collect and use rainwater.
- Whenever possible, install aerators on faucets where no strong water flow is required (such as in lavatories).
- If possible, install low-water consumption toilets
- Educate your guests about how to save water: for instance, post discreet signs to remind them to shut off faucets when not in use, and ask them to accept less frequent towel and linen changes.
- Teach your staff how to communicate these environmental objectives to guests, and post written information in guest rooms.
- If you have a swimming pool, start by installing a system that supplies the lowest possible amount of chlorine needed to ensure water quality. Then, think about using chlorine-free technologies.

1.2 Energy

Energy is one of the highest overhead cost items in a business and in the case of hotels; it is thought to be the second highest operating cost, only after salaries. This high consumption is usually associated with very demanding technologies used, particularly for providing comfort, such as lighting, heating, ventilation and air conditioning units, as well as in laundry rooms, kitchens, and general services areas, such as swimming pools. Investments in more efficient energy uses and improved management practices may lead to significantly lower operating costs and energy bills, with relatively short investment payback periods. Through the use of renewable energy sources, local pollution is reduced, tourist destination quality is maintained, and visitor experience is enhanced. Moreover, efficient energy use and conservation practices contribute to improving company reputation among customers and other sectors concerned with reducing global energy consumption and its impact on climate change and the immediate coastal environment.

Renewable energy sources are characterized by their transformation and utilization processes, which may take up to hundreds of years without being consumed or depleted. These sources include hydro-power (water), solar, wind, and ocean current energies. Furthermore, depending on the way they are used, biomass and geothermal energies may also be classified as renewable. Renewable energies are often split into conventional and non-conventional types. Of the conventional types, the most widely used is large-scale water power, such as that generated by dams. Wind, solar, geothermal, and ocean energies are considered to be non-conventional types. The most readily available source of renewable energy for hotels is solar energy which can be used for water heating, night lawn lighting through special lamps etc.

Solar power comes from directly tapping energy radiated by the sun in order to provide heat and electricity. In solar energy systems, the heat captured in solar collector panels may be used to meet various needs, such as household or industrial hot water, or for heating buildings and agricultural applications, among other things. Photovoltaic panels consisting of a series of solar cells are used to generate electricity, and constitute a feasible solution for supplying power in areas where the available solar resource is abundant. Electricity generated by these systems can either be used directly or stored in batteries to be consumed at night.

Practical Tips

Install energy control instruments, such as meters, real-time power use monitoring systems, timers, photovoltaic cells, etc.

Set up an adequate inspection and maintenance system for wiring, heating, etc.

Make sure insulation of pipes and hot water tanks fits tightly to prevent heat losses.

Use alternative energy (solar, wind, geothermal, water, etc.) systems whenever possible.

Install efficient lighting devices, such as fluorescent lamps and others, particularly in heavily used areas.

When deciding on facilities' design and decoration, you should think about taking advantage of natural light. When use of artificial light is unavoidable, implement energy-saving fixtures and technology.

Make sure there are no hot points or "grounded leaks"; in order to check this, turn all the lights off and unplug all appliances. If the power meter disk keeps on spinning, you need to check your wiring. Remember that a power leak is a money leak.

Do not overload your electrical wiring with multiple outlet power strips or through the use of several appliances plugged into the same wall outlet. Furthermore, do not use extensions because they lead to wiring overload and overheating hazard: this also results in inefficient operation, potential blackouts, short circuits, and long-term damage.

Connections or splices should be firm, and covered with electrician's tape. Do not use adhesive bandages, Scotch tape, or other materials.

Install a ground connection, which consists of a low-resistance conductor connected to the neutral wire of building power feeds through a 10-foot copper rod (Copperweld) sunk into the ground. This action protects electric wiring against any voltage surge that could result from lightning, contact between a high tension line and the company's feeder cables, etc.

Encourage your customers and employees to turn off lights when not needed, as well as TV sets and computer voltage regulators, as well as everything else that is not being used at the time. Battery chargers for cellular phones, video cameras, communication and portable computer equipment (laptops, palm pilots, etc.) consume energy while plugged in, whether or not they are recharging these devices. The same is true for remote control devices, even when they are not on. (Every time you see a light signal on multiple outlet power strips, regulators, or any similar device, it means power is being consumed there.)

Keep curtains and blinds open during the day; natural light is always better. However, in warm climates, close them in the daytime because leaving them open lets natural light in, but also heat. At any rate, the cost of artificial lighting is lower than that of air conditioning the room.

If your goal is to illuminate spaces, paint the walls in light colors. Favor colors with an index above 70% for areas where the tasks performed are mostly visual. Similarly, consider light colors for floors, ceilings, doors, and furniture in general. This helps take better advantage of both natural and artificial light.

If compact fluorescent lamps cannot be installed in areas requiring little illumination (rooms, hallways, cornices), 25-watt (incandescent) light bulbs are recommended. In multiple light bulb lamps, you can remove one of every three light bulbs, or replace them with 25- or 40-watt light bulbs.

Try not to leave light bulbs stronger than 50 watts on during the night.

Turn off all heat-generating appliances –irons, electric hair rollers or curlers, grills, electric cookers, heaters– before you finish using them to take advantage of accumulated heat.

Laundry

Only place the amount of laundry specified as the maximum allowable load into the machine. If you put in less than that you will be wasting water and power; and if you place more than the amount allowed, your laundry will be poorly washed and you may overload the motor.

Always use the shortest possible cycle need for proper laundering.

Try not to use hot water in the washing machine, unless laundry is extremely soiled. Additionally, make sure rinsing is done with cold water.

Only use the smallest possible amount of detergent; too much detergent produces a lot of foam that places an unwarranted additional demand on the motor. It is best to use a controlled foam detergent.

Driers

Only use the drier when strictly necessary.

Take advantage of sunshine to dry your laundry, both eliminating bacteria and saving energy.

Dishwashers

Do not waste dishwasher water to remove food scraps on dishes. If food scraps have hardened, soak the dishes before loading them into the dishwasher.

Make sure the dishwasher is full, but not overloaded. If you only have a few dirty dishes, do not use the “rinse hold” control, since rinsing will take longer and will consume 12-26 liters of hot water per cycle.

Let the dishes air dry; if your dishwasher does not have an air drying setup, turn it off, and leave the door slightly ajar right after the final rinse for faster drying.

Irons

Check the iron surface to make sure it is smooth and clean. This way heat will be transferred in a more uniform manner.

Sprinkle clothing lightly with water without wetting it too much.

Iron the largest possible amount of clothing in each work session. The power required by the iron to heat up will be wasted when ironing only a few garments.

Iron garments requiring less heat first, and then, as the iron becomes hotter, continue with those needing more heat.

Try to do your ironing during the day, so you can save on lighting.

Do not leave the iron on when not in use.

Make sure the iron cord and plug are in good condition.

Vacuumcleaners

Keep vacuum cleaners and suction hoses in good general condition.

Use nozzles that are suitable for the surfaces being vacuumed.

Clean filters after you finish using the vacuum cleaner

Refrigerators

Install the refrigerator in a place where there is enough room for air to flow between the back of the fridge and the wall (5 to 10 cm approximately), and be careful not to place objects that could block airflow; otherwise, the appliance will overwork and consume more power. Do not install the refrigerator in enclosures or in cabinets. The radiator grill in the back must always be ventilated.

Do not use the back of the fridge to dry towels, clothes, or shoes. This will increase power consumption.

Install refrigerators away from heat-generating appliances, such as electric, gas, or firewood stoves, electric or microwave ovens, and from windows where direct sunlight gets through, since their proximity will cause the refrigerator to overwork.

Make sure the refrigerator is leveled. If the fridge base or the floor is uneven, the door gasket will not seal it tightly and warm air will enter the unit.

Make sure the door is properly closed, and do not leave it half open. A refrigerator operates most efficiently when its door is opened as seldom as possible. Thus, decide what you need before opening it, and close it immediately to prevent warm air from coming in and cold air from escaping. Do not open the fridge unnecessarily, or keep it open for more than 10 seconds.

Keep liquids in covered containers in order to prevent moisture due to evaporation, since this will accumulate in the freezer in the form of frost.

Food packaged in thick paper containers should be taken out and placed in thin plastic bags. Vegetables with a high moisture content and peeled fruits should also be kept in thin bags. It is best to clean them and not keep them in the fridge too long.

Keep the freezer as full as possible, since frozen food helps conserve the cold. If at a particular time you do not have enough food to put in the freezer, fill some containers with water, cover them with lids, and put them in the freezer.

Periodically clean the back of the unit (particularly the condenser). A dirty condenser back grill can increase appliance operating costs. Grills on the back or lower front of the unit should be checked and cleaned at least twice a year. Keep these grills thoroughly ventilated and free from objects that block airflow.

Gas Stoves

Line all surfaces around the burners with aluminum foil to reflect heat upwards.

Make sure burner combustion is taking place with the proper amount of air. A yellow or orange flame is a sign of inefficient combustion; therefore, you must regulate burner air inflow until the flames turn blue.

Use pots and frying pans that cover the burner completely, so the flame will heat their entire bottom surface.

Put lids on your pots to trap steam, since food will cook faster. Covered pots not only prevent splashes on the range top, but also take better advantage of heat and make cooking faster.

When water or any other liquid food begins to boil, lower the burner heat intensity at least to half. Boiling at a faster rate will not cook food quicker but will instead consume the water contained in food and you will waste fuel.

Turn off the oven a few minutes before food is ready to take out; the oven will retain the temperature needed to finish cooking the food.

Water Heaters

Best option is to make use of the sun energy and use solar water heaters.

Installing the water heater as near as possible to the place where hot water will be used is important. Otherwise, during the water heater's entire useful life which can be many years!– hot water will take longer to reach the area where it will be used, will lose heat along the way, and you will be paying more than you should on your utility bills.

If you have an automatic heater, keep it at the minimum setting (lukewarm or warm).

Airconditioners

Ask your guests to keep doors and windows closed in their rooms while the air conditioning unit is on, and to unplug it or turn it off when leaving the room.

Check the unit periodically to see whether it needs refrigerant gas. Preferably, have a technician do the checking and refilling, if necessary.

Carry out thorough cleaning of the unit: remove dust and mildew, and paint the unit to prevent rusting.

Make sure the motor, wiring, and thermostat are working properly.

Clean the air filter every 15 days. Dirty filters and dusty motor casings result in motor overload and reduce usefulness.

Provide maintenance to the equipment every year. Air conditioning units without maintenance for two or more years have been found to consume twice the power.

Thermal insulation can save you up to 50% of the energy used in heating or air conditioning.

1.3 Coastal Environment and Biodiversity

Flora and fauna are the living components of nature, which, together with nonliving components such as water, air, etc., comprise the natural environment.

Life on earth exhibits a seemingly endless diversity. Living beings have conquered such different environments such as oceans and the air; they have settled in warm and humid tropical belts, as well as in cold and arid polar areas. In order to face the challenges presented by locomotion, food, or reproduction, they have displayed an overwhelming variety of solutions. Life's diversity, the result of 4 billion years of evolution, is earth's greatest treasure.

Practical Tips

Keep information available about the most important local species in the region. If possible, establish a small library with naturalist guidebooks, national park information, etc., and make these available to your guests.

If there are lists of native species typical of your area, include them in your library. Otherwise, find a way to develop these lists, perhaps through volunteer students or professionals willing to collaborate.

Find out about mechanisms through which your company and visitors could help support conservationist organizations working in the area.

Do not use high-intensity light bulbs for outdoor illumination. Install discreet insect-repelling lights, if possible.

If your facilities have large glass windows, place silhouettes and stickers on them to prevent flying birds from crashing into the glass and being injured.

Try establishing natural barriers such as hedges to regulate the amount of noise and light issuing from your facilities, particularly if your building is within or near a highly sensitive protected area, such as egg-laying beaches and nesting sites.

Require your guides to educate visitors in how to behave properly while observing flora and fauna. If you do not personally provide the service, make sure your tour guides take all the necessary steps to ensure a responsible and sustainable operation.

As much as possible, take advantage of natural environmental conditions to create spaces to educate guests at your facilities, for instance, by creating showcase orchards or gardens.

If possible, get involved in creating and maintaining biological corridors; this way you will be able to increase the likelihood of visitors enjoying the local fauna in a responsible manner.

Do not under any circumstances feed local wildlife, because this practice fosters reliance on humans, alters their natural diet, and may encourage disease transmission.

Get informed about the main flora and fauna conservation laws in your area, and make these known to your guests and staff.

In the case of areas where hunting or fishing is allowed, always respect the closed season and its regulations.

Make a commitment to ensure your customers also abide by these regulations.

1.4 Lawns, Landscaped Areas and Gardens

Natural spaces, open spaces, or landscaped areas by transpiring water; altering wind speed, shading areas, and modifying heat storage and exchange between urban surfaces, trees affect local climate, and consequently the use of energy in buildings, as well as human thermal comfort and air quality.

By providing air cooling shade in the summer and blocking winds in the winter, trees can decrease the amount of energy needed to heat and cool buildings. However, depending on their location, they can also increase heat requirements during the winter in tree-shaded buildings. The energy conservation effects produced by trees vary according to a region's climate and the layout or arrangement of trees around buildings. Energy-saving tree arrangements provide shade primarily on east and west walls and roofs, and wherever they protect against predominant winter winds. Energy use in a tree-shaded house may be 20 or 25% lower than in a similar home surrounded only by open spaces.

Trees which are improperly arranged around buildings may actually increase energy requirements and, hence, CO₂ emissions. Thus, in assessing overall tree influence on atmospheric CO₂ levels, various factors need to be taken into consideration, such as the use of fossil fuels in managing vegetation, the carbon cycle involving the trees themselves, and CO₂ emissions from power plants. Trees remove gas pollutants from air mainly through leaf stomas, although some gases are removed by the plant's surface. Once inside leaves, gases are diffused around intercellular spaces and can be absorbed by membranes of water to form acids or react in the internal surfaces of leaves. Trees also remove pollution by intercepting air-borne particles. Some particles may be absorbed within the tree, although most are retained on the plant surface.

Practical Tips

Identify your area's main typical plant species. To this end, you should get in touch with a professional or with local people. Use these plants in landscaping your premises.

You can use this information in determining which plants you are going to have in your garden, labeling trail signs, and preparing relevant information (common and scientific names, traditional uses, range, etc.).

If you use ornamental plants that do not come from the area, be careful to prevent their spreading to other places. The most important trees should be labeled to show their common and scientific names.

Remember that signs should not be nailed directly on trees and should be visible.

Either purchase or make your own natural fertilizers and repellents.

If you wish to make your own fertilizer, you can build a composter. This is a simple ventilated wooden framework that rests directly on the ground. It must have a cover to prevent fly proliferation and breeding.

1.5 Solid Waste

Rejecting

This means not purchasing any product that, on account of its origin or shape, is harmful to the environment.

Reducing

The basic principle of every waste management program and any serious commitment to the environment consists of reducing over-consumption of products, particularly those generating hard-to-recycle waste, such as polyethylene packaging for single-use food items. Make sure to purchase durable, high quality items, and try not to buy disposable products.

Reusing

Through this principle, waste generation can be avoided or decreased. Packaging and products that have fulfilled their purpose are often discarded. Reusing such items consists of finding a new function for them, wondering what they can be used for. There are countless possibilities, such as using them as flower vases, or for organizing and classifying things such as buttons, nails, pins, etc.

Repairing

When a product stops working due to any failure, it can be repaired and then reused, thus precluding the possibility of its becoming discarded junk.

Recycling

This means taking a product that has already fulfilled its purpose and lost its usefulness, and viewing it as raw material for new goods which may have either the same or a different function.

Practical Tips

- Motivate your staff to find creative ways of reducing the amount of waste generated by your company.
- Think about purchasing goods in large bulk quantities, instead of single-use packages.
- Provide rooms with soap, shampoo, and toilet paper dispensers.
- Take the very best advantage of all available resources.
- Eliminate the use of hazardous or ecologically toxic compounds. Replace them with biodegradable cleaners and detergents.
- Acquire solar energy-powered devices, such as calculators and clocks.
- Look for these and other environmental symbols on the products you acquire.

Recyclable material: this means the material used in manufacturing the product can be recycled

Recyclable material: this shows the product was made from previously used material

This is a product that has not been tested on animals

Organic product: this refers to food items that are produced without toxic agrochemicals or chemical preservatives

- ④ Develop and implement a reuse program. For instance, take advantage of organic waste to produce fertilizer; print paper on both sides, reuse printed paper for making notes or for other minor uses, and only purchase products sold in returnable packages.
- ④ Enter into product repackaging agreements with suppliers. Use fabric instead of paper napkins, keeping in mind the large number of trees required to manufacture
- ④ paper.
- ④ Reuse empty packages for storing things.
- ④ Reuse old garments for cleaning tasks.
- ④ Use biodegradable toilet paper, cosmetics, detergents, etc.
- ④ To the extent possible, use recycled products, such as stationery and office paper, as well as paper for decorations, etc.
- ④ Keep records of the types and amount of waste your company generates, according to operating area.
- ④ Make your staff and guests aware of how important it is to adequately manage waste.
- ④ Encourage customers not to use disposable plastic items, much less dump such products in protected areas.
- ④ Try sorting waste at the source, for instance, in guests rooms and the kitchen.
- ④ Provide labeled bins with lids to sort and deposit recyclable waste such as aluminum, plastics, glass, paper, and organic materials.
- ④ Make sure waste bin locations are easily spotted by visitors and staff.
- ④ Create an adequate place for storing waste before its final disposal.

1.6 Pollution and Its Prevention

Pollution is the presence of harmful and bothersome substances deposited in air; water; and soil by human activity in such quantity and quality they may interfere with the health and well-being of people, animals, and plants, or prevent full enjoyment of life. The sources of pollution can be highly varied substances in solid, liquid, and gas forms, as well as noise, heat, and odors. Pollution in every form is always a delicate issue for a sustainable tourism industry, since it causes human health problems, affects the environment, creates foul odors, and projects a negative image of the enterprise. Each company should have the proper systems and mechanisms in place to prevent or reduce the release of harmful emissions and waste, including wastewater, as well as noise and visual contamination.

Practical Tips

- ④ Use wastewater treatment systems. One of the most widely used methods is the septic tank. While it can operate very well, it does not allow water recovery and subsequent reuse.
- ④ Make sure your wastewater is not released directly into local waters (rivers, lakes, and reservoirs, among others).
- ④ Remember surface water is linked to ground water. Any surface pollution may contaminate ground water, and vice versa
- ④ Channel rainwater but care should be taken not to damage plant cover. Avoid building straight canals with steep slopes or large-area inclines that increase water speed and produce erosion. Prevent channeled water (from roofs, roof gutters, street gutters, etc.) from falling directly and heavily on surfaces that are subject to erosion.
- ④ Take advantage of rainwater: build storage tanks, use it for laundering, gardening, cleaning public areas, toilets, and other applications.

1.7 Composting an Alternative to Waste Dumping

Composting occurs through the decomposition of organic wastes to make an earthy, dark, crumbly substance that is excellent for adding to plants or enriching garden soil. It is the way to recycle your yard and kitchen wastes, and is a critical step in reducing the volume of garbage needlessly sent to landfills for disposal. Moreover composting can be an additional source of revenue for hotels to help them in their environmental sustainability quest.

Achieving good composting needs the provision of the proper environmental conditions for microbial life. Compost is made by the action of billions of microbes (fungi, bacteria, etc.) that digest the yard and kitchen wastes. One characteristics of the decomposition process is heat generation and so do not be alarmed if the compost piles becomes warm or even hot at times. However a cool compost pile will house enough, worms, insects, and their relatives to help out the microbes. All of these will slowly make compost out of your yard and kitchen wastes under any conditions. For proper composting these living things need air, water, and food. Propoerly maintained piles turns into compost much more quickly.

Air – it is important to make sure that there are plenty of air passageways into the compost pile. Some compost ingredients, such as green grass clippings or wet leaves, mat down very easily into slimy layers that air cannot get through. Other ingredients, such as straw, don't mat down easily and are very helpful in allowing air into the center of a pile. To make sure that the adequate aeration for the pile and its microbes, thoroughly break

up or mix in any ingredients that might mat down and exclude air. The pile can be turned to get air into it, which means completely breaking it apart with a spade or garden fork and then piling it back together in a more 'fluffed-up' condition.

Water - , The pile should be as moist as a wrung-out sponge to fit the needs of compost microbes. At this moisture level, there is a thin film of water coating every particle in the pile, making it very easy for microbes to live and disperse themselves throughout the pile.

There are two major kinds of food that composting microbes need.

'Browns' are dry and dead plant materials such as straw, dry brown weeds, autumn leaves, and wood chips or sawdust. These materials are mostly made of chemicals that are just long chains of sugar molecules linked together. As such, these items are a source of energy for the compost microbes. Because they tend to be dry, browns often need to be moistened before they are put into a compost system.

'Greens' are fresh (and often green) plant materials such as green weeds from the garden, kitchen fruit and vegetable scraps, green leaves, coffee grounds and tea bags, fresh horse manure, etc. Compared to browns, greens have more nitrogen in them. Nitrogen is a critical element in amino acids and proteins, and can be thought of as a protein source for the billions of multiplying microbes.

A good mix of browns and greens is the best nutritional balance for the microbes. This mix also helps out with the aeration and amount of water in the pile. Browns, for instance, tend to be bulky and promote good aeration. Greens, on the other hand, are typically high in moisture, and balance out the dry nature of the browns.

Compostable materials - grass/lawn clippings, hay, kitchen wastes, leaves, straw, weeds and other garden wastes, wood chips and sawdust.

Non-Compostable materials - chemically-treated wood products, diseased plants, human wastes, meat, bones, and fatty food wastes, pernicious weeds, pet wastes

There are a numerous options for containing the compost. Some people choose to go binless, simply building a compost pile in a convenient spot on the ground. Others build bins from materials such as recycled pallets, or two-by-fours and plywood.

1.1.1 Structures for Composting

A **barrel or drum composter** generates compost in a relatively short period of time and provides an easy mechanism for turning. This method requires a barrel of at least 55 gallons with a secure lid. Drill six to nine rows of 1/2-inch holes over the length of the barrel to allow for air circulation and drainage of excess moisture. Place the barrel upright on blocks to allow bottom air circulation, fill it three quarters full with organic waste material, and add about 1/4-cup of a high nitrogen containing fertilizer. If needed, apply water until moist. Every few days, turn the drum on its side and roll it around the yard to mix and aerate the compost. The lid can be removed after turning to allow for air penetration. Ideally, the compost should be ready in two to four months.

Bin-type structures are the most practical for larger quantities of organic waste. The bin should be about four to five feet in diameter and at least four feet high. A stake may be driven in the middle of the bin before adding material to help maintain the shape of the pile and to facilitate adding water

A three-chambered bin is a very efficient and durable structure for fast composting. It holds a considerable amount of compost and allows good air circulation. The three-chambered bin works on an assembly line idea, having three batches of compost in varying stages of decomposition. To make this structure, it is best to use rot-resistant wood, such as redwood or cedar, or a combination of wood and metal posts. Unless the wood is rot resistant, it will decompose within a few years. Each bin should be about five feet by three feet and about four to five feet high. This volume is ideal for maintaining heat and at the same time is manageable for turning. Using removable doors in the front offers complete access to the contents for turning.

2 Introduction to EMS

Why does your company need an Environmental Management Plan (EMP)? An EMP will help keep track of all activities related to environmental management in your organization. These activities can be better streamlined and organized thus keeping time and effort employees have to devote to such activities at a reasonable level. The EMP will make environmental management easier and more natural for everyone in your business. Employees appreciate that the EMP spells out exactly what is expected of them. EMP provides the general framework to ensure your business is in compliance with environmental regulations. Such a plan allows you to easily spot opportunities for improvement and make cost savings that may even take your business beyond compliance. Finally, implementing an EMP in your organization will facilitate development of an Environmental Management System (EMS) that could eventually be certified or recognized by relevant authorities.

Mauritius is a popular tourism destination for people from around the world. Apart from its natural physical assets as a tropical island, it is also distinguished by its exotic sandy beaches, blue lagoons, good climate, a spectacular landscape and make Mauritius a dream island for tourists. The tourist industry in Mauritius shares a close link and is highly dependent on the physical environment. It must therefore, for its continued existence, be at the forefront of actions directed towards the protection and preservation of the environment.

Past experience has clearly indicated that sound environmental practices in hotel management result in substantial savings on operational costs whilst increasing market share and enhancing corporate image. However, the apparent complexity involved in the implementation of Best Environment Practices (BEP) can intimidate more than one hotel manager.

Example of a Hotel

Name of Hotel: **Mauritian Dodo Hotel**

Address & Contact: **Royal Road, Flic En Flac. Mr Ti-Jean**

Location: **500 Mts from the Beach**

Detail of services/facilities: **Rooms, 1 Restaurant, 1 Laundry, Spa & Pool**

Number of rooms: **20**

2.1 EMS Best practices Main Goals

 Integrate the environment as one component of day-to-day hotel management

 Identify significant and priority measures for hotels, enabling their implementation and ensuring sustainability over time

 Promote rational and eco-efficient use of resources

 Given hotels the opportunity to make the first steps towards an integrated environmental management system (ISO 14001:2004)

2.2 EMS Best practices Management Plan

BEP Management Plan helps in keeping track of all activities related to environment management. This plan enables management to better organise and streamline activities to keep the time and effort employees have to devote to them at a reasonable level. It also provides a general framework to ensure business operations are in compliance with environment regulations through proper record keeping, clearly established procedures and up to date training. In order to generate a BEP Management Plan, an Environment Team needs to be constituted to look into all aspects of environmental management that needs to be taken into consideration for drafting of such a plan.

2.3 EMS Best practices Benefits to Society

- ✓ Protection of natural environment
- ✓ Decrease use of land, water and energy
- ✓ Reduce risks of industrial accidents and emissions

2.4 EMS Best practices Benefits to companies

EMS Best Practices provides a comprehensive approach to environmental management as it considers environmental impact of business operations throughout the entire life cycle of its products. The benefits from its implementation are as follows:

- ✓ Enhance image and reputation of company towards all stakeholders (customers, employees, government, etc.)
- ✓ Create long term customer loyalty and increase marketing scope
- ✓ Improve operational efficiency, that is, reduce costs linked to use of raw materials, water, energy and other costs such as for offsite disposal of waste generated.
- ✓ Improve goodwill and public image

2.5 EMS Best Practices Definitions

While it is good to avoid unnecessary jargon and acronyms, it helps to have a shared understanding of a few terms so that everyone in your company understands how the Environmental Management Plan works and what their role is. Defined words are italicized throughout the document.

+ **Applicable Laws**

Local laws, rules, regulations, requirements, and policies governing protection of the environment and protection of public health and safety.

+ **Aspects**

Element of an organization's activities, products or services which can interact with the environment. Examples: Spills, Chemical release, air emission, water usage

+ **Best Management Practices (BMPs)**

Good practices that apply the most up-to-date knowledge and technology to achieve and maintain a level of environmental performance that goes beyond what is necessary to comply with applicable laws.

+ **Corrective Action**

A specific way to correct an existing problem or non-conformance when performance deviates from expectations set out in the EMP.

+ **Critical**

A term we use in this workbook to indicate the responsibility, goal, function, or element of the EMP necessary to make sure your company handles spills properly, keeps its employees safe, and stays in compliance with environmental regulations.

✦ **Environmental Management Plan (EMP)**

The actions an organization is taking to determine how it affects the environment, complies with regulations, keeps track of environmental management activities, and meets environmental goals and targets. It also documents key elements of environmental management including the environmental policy, responsibilities, environmental manual, applicable standard operating procedures and BMPs, recordkeeping, document control, reports, communication, training, monitoring, and corrective action.

✦ **Environmental Management System (EMS)**

An organizational approach to environmental management that incorporates quality improvement principles (sometimes referred to as "Plan-Do-Check-Act") to develop, achieve, review, and maintain an environmental policy. Broad EMS elements include planning, implementation, checking and corrective action, and management review.

✦ **Environmental Manual**

The collection of information that identifies applicable laws and outlines the organization's approach to complying with or exceeding their requirements.

✦ **Environmental Policy**

A statement of the organization's commitment to the environment. It is at the heart of the EMS and the framework for planning and action undertaken through the EMS.

✦ **Goal**

A general statement of a desired outcome to be achieved through the business' EMP.

✦ **Impact**

Any change to the environment, whether positive or negative, wholly or partially resulting from an organization's activities, products or services. Examples: water contamination, air pollution, recycling

✦ **Important**

A term used in this workbook to indicate the responsibility, goal, function, or element of the EMP that helps your company be efficient or proactive, to save money or time, or increase the respect and goodwill of employees and community members.

✦ **Preventive Action**

A specific way to keep a problem or non-conformance with the EMP from recurring in the future.

✦ **Process Map**

A picture or diagram that shows the flow of materials through the business, including what comes in (inputs) and what goes out (outputs, including wastes).

✦ **Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)**

A set procedure used to carry out a specific activity or operation. It usually includes a step-by-step breakdown of how and when a task is performed on a day to day basis. SOPs are usually written and filed or posted in an accessible location.

✦ **Target**

A specific statement that conveys a measurable degree of progress toward a particular goal.

2.6 EMS Best Practices Laws and Regulations

The "Laws" includes the rules, regulations, requirements and policies governing the Protection of the Environment and Public Health & Safety. Why comply with environmental regulations? The most obvious reason is to avoid severe penalties associated with non-compliance. Government Inspectors have the right to make on site visits at any time to verify whether business operations are in line with laws in force. In case of non compliance, the Government can order immediate corrective measures to be taken and even, in extreme case, issue a "stop order" to temporarily cease your business operations i.e until appropriate corrective actions have been taken. This is normally over and above legal action that can be initiated for non compliance which may result in severe fines being imposed by the courts.

Below is a list of applicable laws for hotel in Mauritius:

1. The tourism Act 2006
2. The Tourism Employee Welfare Fund Act
3. Environment Protection Act 2008
4. Road Traffic (Vehicular Emissions) Regulations 2002
5. Environment Protection (Effluent Discharge Permit) 2003
6. Plastic Carry Bags Regulation 2004
7. Control of Noise regulation 2008
8. Waste Oil Regulation 2006
9. Beach Authority Act 2002
10. Industrial Waste Regulation 2008
11. Occupational Safety and Health Act 2005
12. Labour Act 2008

3.3 Hotel Organization Structure and EMS Best practices

Having roles and responsibility clearly written helps employees understand which environmental management activities they are responsible for and how their role relates to the roles of others. EMS Best Practices helps to increase accountability within the company and motivates employees to take more personal responsibility for environmental management because the tasks are well defined and not overwhelming.

Each business is unique and has to work out environmental roles and responsibilities in a way that fits into its particular organisation structure and culture. When assigning responsibilities, it may be helpful to distinguish between critical and important ones. It is also beneficial to find a balance of responsibilities among all employees so that environmental management will not take up too much individual time and will truly be a team effort.

Defined environmental responsibilities, signed by the Company owner, need to be communicated among the employees with a copy in their personal file. This way, employees are reassured that they are within the scope of their job when doing assigned environmental duties.

Spread responsibilities among employees. For example:

1. Each manager could be responsible for all environmental requirements within her/his department or
2. Different individuals could specialise in different environmental responsibilities across the entire company

3.4 Environment Responsibilities Worksheet

3.4.1 Assignment of Environmental Responsibilities

Position	Environmental Responsibilities	Designation (critical or important)

3.5 Mauritian DODO Hotel Organisation Structure

3.6 Example of Environmental Responsibility Assignments

Position	Environmental Responsibilities
EMS Best Practice Coordinator	<p>Critical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oversee environmental policy and Environmental Management Plan (EMP). • Oversee environmental manual. • Serve as primary contact for regulatory inspectors. • Commit resources to achieve environmental goals. <p>Important</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review audit results and progress on achieving goals and revise EMP as needed. • Update employees annually on environmental policy and goals. • Incorporate environmental procedures into patron contracts.
All Employees	<p>Critical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attend training on and understand role in emergency action plan. • Attend training on and follow environmental Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) • Best Management Practices (BMPs). • Participate in annual review of marina environmental policy and goals.
Store Manager	<p>Critical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educate patrons about environmental concerns related to product use, equipment rental, and maintenance activities. <p>Important</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with appropriate marina employees to evaluate effectiveness of environmentally sound products. • Stock environmentally sound products that have proven to be effective.
Maintenance Manager	<p>Critical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oversee management of wastes generated by employee activities and compile quarterly waste data reports. • Perform sampling required by wastewater permit and submit reports. <p>Important</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor employees' use of environmental SOPs and BMP's.
Maintenance Technician	<p>Critical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct weekly hazardous waste container inspections. • Perform quarterly visual inspections as required by storm water permit. <p>Important</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor oil/water separator for malfunction daily.

Position	Environmental Responsibilities

3.7 EMS Commitment

- ✓ Develop and maintain an effective environmental management systems
- ✓ Minimise adverse effects of our business processes on the environment
- ✓ Monitor, control, and record environmental hazards as required by relevant regulations.
- ✓ Allow effective examinations (for e.g. energy sources, lighting, ventilation, water waste and refuse disposal)
- ✓ Dispose dangerous material according to relevant regulations
- ✓ Educate and train employees to act in an environmentally responsible manner

3.8 Environment Policy

Your Environment Policy provides and promotes the interchange of information about your environmental commitments among all stakeholders (employees, management, public, client, local council, shareholders, neighbours, etc) to enable services to be delivered in an environmentally friendly manner:

An Environment Policy begins with a declaration of your hotel's commitment to the protection of the environment. This includes prevention of pollution and continual improvement in environmental management performance as well as your commitment towards your employees and community members.

Furthermore, your Environment Policy is useful to communicate your business unique culture towards environment management to local officials, customers and others outside stakeholders.

An Environment Policy worksheet (below) can be used to create an environment policy. This policy need to be periodically reviewed and improved.

3.9 Environment Policy Worksheet

3.9.1 Environment Policy Examples

Mauritian Dodo Hotel 1 Environment Policy

The Mauritian Dodo Hotel is committed to the implementation of proactive measures to help protect and sustain the local, national and global environment for future generations. The Hotel aims to achieve the objective of improved environmental performance through pollution prevention, increased staff awareness and continuous improvement.

Mauritian Dodo Hotel 2 Environment Policy

The Mauritian Dodo Hotel 2 is an environmentally conscious hotel. We not only aim to provide exceptional quality services for our guests, but are committed to the implementation of proactive measures to help protect and sustain the local, national and global environment for future generations. By working together we can create a safe and clean environment and ensure that environmental issues are kept at the forefront of everyone's mind and given proper attention at all times. Some of the steps we have taken to be 'green' are:

- Use 30% recycled paper and making double sided photo copies whenever possible
- Use biodegradable detergents that contain no phosphates
- Recycle fluorescent light bulbs, paper, cardboard, toner and ink jet cartridges
- Use compact fluorescent light bulbs in guest rooms and wherever possible
- Compliant with the local Environment Act
- Grow herbs for use in all food and beverage outlets
- Formed Environmental Committee that meets regularly

4 Documenting EMS Best Practices Procedures

4.1 Making Progress over Time – Setting Goals

Goal is a general statement of a desired outcome to be achieved through the business EMP. The setting of goals helps to improve environmental management performance by connecting your EMP to the day-to-day business activities of your enterprise. Goals are linked to the environmental policy and provide a vision of the direction you want to go in over the long term. Goals should be realistic and fit within the mission and overall business strategy of your company.

Identify those goals that are critical to your business' environmental performance and tackle those first. For example, confirming compliance with environmental regulations and putting systems in place to maintain compliance may be a critical priority. There may also be waste reduction or water or energy conservation activities that are compelling because of the potential for large cost savings for your business.

4.1.1 Worksheet for Setting Goals

Step 1

Brainstorm a list of possible goals to improve your company's environmental management. They may have to do with compliance or they may be about reducing your business' use of resources, or preventing impacts to the environment. Don't worry about the difficulty of achieving a goal or its relative importance during the brainstorming session. List the goals you come up with in the left column of the Environmental Goals to consider Table 1.0

Step 2

Go over the list of goals you developed during Step 1. For each goal, decide whether it is critical (necessary to keep employees safe, prevent and respond to spills, or achieve compliance), or important (helps your company manage its environmental affairs more efficiently and proactively, save money, and increase the respect and goodwill of employees and community members). Indicate its significance in the middle column of the Table 1.0.

Step 3

For each goal, indicate in the right hand column the degree of difficulty involved with achieving the goal. Consider the budget, number of staff, degree of effort, and other resources needed to achieve the goal.

Step 4

Select at least three goals to work on for the next several months to a year: Critical goals should be your first priority. If these issues are under control, consider selecting the goals that have the biggest return for the invested effort. If you can't come to agreement, then the Environmental Team can vote on them or you, as the business owner, can decide.

Table 1. Environmental Goals to Consider

Goal	Significance ¹	Difficulty ²

Significance¹ = critical or important

Difficulty² = high, average, low

4.1.2 Example of Goals

Figure 1. Mauritian Dodo Hotel Goal

Mauritian Dodo Hotel Goal

1. Verify compliance with all environmental regulations.
2. Verify the appropriate management of all waste streams.
3. Communicate the environmental policy to all employees.

Figure 2. Dodo Hotel Goal

Mauritian Dodo Hotel Goal

1. Update Emergency Response Plan.
2. Reduce hazardous waste.
3. Reduce energy use.
4. Communicate the environmental policy to all employees.

4.2 Record Keeping

There are several reasons to keep good records of your environmental management activities. In the course of an inspection, most inspectors start with a close look at your environmental record keeping. Having proper records in hand helps your business get off on the right foot. For this reason, when getting organized, begin by looking at which records are needed to meet regulatory requirements. Thereafter, you can decide which additional information is important and how records should be kept. Examples of the different types of situation where records are required:

- Records useful during an urgent situation involving your businesses' environmental impact matters such as a spill or a complaint from the neighbours;
- Records essential to protect your business from legal and financial hassles down the road;
- Records to substantiate whether your business is performing to the level it committed to in its EMP; and
- Records to provide valuable data on business performance, or would be helpful in demonstrating to your customers that your business is "green"

On the next page is an example master file list that gives you a simple system to organize your environmental management files and records that go along with EMP and environmental manual. It covers the most common environmental recordkeeping requirements. However, to make sure nothing is missing, be sure to go back to your environmental manual and review the required documents and records listed in each section to make sure they are included in your master file list.

4.3 Sample Master File List

4.3.1 *Emergency Preparedness (Record retention time – 3 years)*

- Emergency call list and decision tree.
- Spill reporting call list.
- Copies of emergency plans such as hazardous waste contingency plan; spill prevention, control, and countermeasure (SPCC) plan; and storm water spill preparedness plan.
- Summary of annual emergency plan exercises.
- Documentation and critique of incidents that triggered emergency plan.
- Reports of spills to regulatory agencies.

4.3.2 *Training Records (Record retention time – lifetime of employee + 10 years)*

While many different environmental regulations require training, most companies find it easiest to organize them according to employee. In each employee's file include:

- Position description including environmental responsibilities.

- Training plan (see Section on Training for information on how to develop employee training plans).
- Training certificates and the agendas or topics list for each training session, in chronological order; with the most recent training first.

4.3.3 Waste Management (Record retention time – 3 years)

- Correspondence with regulators (inspection reports, regulatory interpretations, and other correspondence).
- EPA Generator ID number(s).
- Current hazardous waste permit and associated documents and correspondence.
- Records of waste determination.
- Hazardous waste shipment paperwork.
- Special waste shipment paperwork such as universal waste batteries, lamps, and mercury switches, used oil, PCB and non-PCB ballasts.
- Solid waste tipping records.
- Inspection records.

4.3.4 Air Management (Record retention time – 3 years)

- Correspondence with regulators (inspection reports, regulatory interpretations, and other correspondence).
- Current permits for major or minor sources and associated documents and correspondence.
- Emission calculations for potential to emit (PTE).
- Annual air toxics inventory.
- Inspection records and chemical usage records as required by permit conditions (e.g., VOC records, pressure drop inspections, operating hours).

4.3.5 Wastewater Management (Record retention time – 3 years)

- Correspondence with local wastewater treatment plant authority.
- Copy of current sanitary sewer ordinance.
- Pre-treatment permit (if applicable) and associated documents and correspondence.

4.3.6 Storm Water Management (Record retention time – 3 years)

- Inventory of storm water drainage and outfalls from your property (include map).
- Storm water pollution prevention plan.
- Maintenance plan for storm water infrastructure.
- Storm water permits (if applicable) and associated documents and correspondence.
- Storm water annual reports and sampling results (if applicable).

4.4 Master schedule of Reports, Notification and Permits

This part of your EMP lists what reports your business is required to file with regulatory agencies to comply with environmental regulations. You should also keep track of additional notifications to regulatory agencies that your business has made, such as reports of spills or releases, or filing with EPA as a generator of hazardous waste. The reason you want to get these issues organized is to prevent your business finding itself in a vulnerable position by missing a regulatory deadline or failing to submit a permit application on time which could potentially cause a permit lapse that could disrupt operations. Here are examples of some (but not all) of these reports and notifications:

Type of Report	Frequency
Notification of hazardous waste activity.	One-time with updates as needed.
Hazardous waste activity report.	Annual or biannual.
Air emissions permit application.	One-time periodic renewals.
Annual air emission inventory.	Annual.
Petroleum Storage Tank registrations.	One-time and change-in-service notifications.
Emergency planning report.	Annual

If any of your activities require an environmental permit, you also need to keep track of when the permit will expire so you can submit an application for renewal or close it out in a timely way. If you are not certain what reports, notifications, and permit applications your business is required to file, this would be an excellent time to seek assistance from the relevant Government authorities to help you get started. In addition to reports that you must submit to regulatory agencies, there are likely to be reports that you need to prepare internally that provide data and information necessary to fill out the required report. You may also produce internal reports to provide information needed to track progress toward meeting goals. Once you are aware of all the reports and notifications that your business needs to maintain, you need a simple system to manage them. Work through the following worksheet to develop an Environmental Master Schedule to help keep track of what needs to be done when and by whom. Include as part of the annual cycle a review of current regulatory requirements to see if reporting or notification requirements have changed.

4.5 Communication

If your business is very small, communication about environmental matters among employees may be accomplished in the natural course of day-to-day interactions. But, for many businesses, making sure everyone who has a need to know stays in the loop requires some dedicated effort. This section explains the part of your EMP that will make sure that employees and supervisors stay involved with environmental management, understand your business' environmental policy, and can provide a consistent message about your business' commitment to environmental performance. It will also make sure your business is providing information to employees and others as required by regulations. As your EMP comes together and your business develops a track record of environmental excellence, you may also wish to more actively promote your business' EMP with customers and community officials. This can be added to the Communication Plan when you feel ready to do so.

4.5.1 Communication Plan Worksheet

Step 1

Identify ways to inform all the employees at your business about the EMP and its goals and list them in the Internal Communication Opportunities table on the next page. To get this information out efficiently, you may want to look for opportunities through existing business meetings or events.

Step 2

Identify all the people outside of your company who need to, or would be interested to, know about your business' EMP. State at least one reason why it would be strategic or beneficial for your business to inform them of the EMP.

Step 3

Referring to the information you developed in Steps 1 and 2, decide who will be included in the Communication Plan for the coming year; how you are going to get the information to them, and who will be responsible. Organize this information using the table on page 57. (Helpful hint: If you do not feel your business is ready to present its EMP "to the world," you can leave out people listed in Step 2 until next year; when you can consider this question again.)

4.5.2 Mauritian Dodo communication Plan

Date Issued	Date Revised
January 2009	February 2009

Who?	What?	How and When?	Person Responsible
Staff	EMP and goals and targets.	Update during annual meeting	Owner
Community	Environmental commitment. New environmental efforts.	Annual picnic on Marina grounds. Policy posted on docks, at entrance, And in office. Host student field trips.	Hotel Manager
All employees	Environmental policy and Current goals.	Presentation during annual meeting. Updates in business newsletter.	Business owner. Human resources Manager.

CURRENT COMMUNICATION PLAN

Date Issued	Date Revised

Who?	What?	How and When?	Person Responsible

4.6 Training

Getting employees trained in everything they need to know to carry out their environmental management responsibilities is one of the biggest challenges facing a small business owner. Training is required by many environmental regulations. Employees need to understand how their responsibilities contribute toward meeting the goals of your EMP if you are going to make progress.

Here are some suggestions for setting up an effective training program. While getting the training program established, set priorities so that you work on getting critical training in place first:

1. *Train those who handle chemicals on what to do if there is a spill or release;*
2. *Make sure you have training programs as required by regulations; and*
3. *Train employees on good practices that improve efficiency, save time or money, or help your business be proactive.*

Use your environmental manual to determine what training is required by applicable laws to develop a comprehensive list of training requirements. Then, refer back to the Assignment of Environmental Responsibilities table to set up training so that each employee gets the training he or she needs, but does not sit through training they don't need.

The Training Plan itself should include what training needs to happen, what type of training it will be, and who is responsible. There should also be a target date and a completion date for each task in your Training Plan. It is usually easiest to set up a Training Plan for the coming year. After that you can review training requirements and revise the plan on an annual basis.

4.6.1 Training Plan Worksheet

4.7 Keeping your EMP Alive and Well

This part of the EMP helps you verify if you are on the right course and gives you a method for getting back on course if you find you have strayed.

There are three components to monitoring:

1. *Environmental compliance monitoring,*
2. *Environmental performance monitoring, and*
3. *Management review and corrective action.*

4.7.1 Environmental Compliance Monitoring

This function determines whether your business is in compliance with regulations and whether employees are following SOPs and BMPs that contribute to compliance. Audits are a good way to determine compliance with regulations and to observe whether employees are following SOPs and BMPs. These can be done internally or by an outside party. You can enlist supervisors to do performance checks in the course of their daily work. It is a good idea to conduct a comprehensive compliance audit every few years to help ensure that you have not overlooked any new activities within your company that may affect the environment or any new or changed regulatory requirements. The Compliance Monitoring Worksheet will help you set priorities and assign responsibility for audits.

4.7.2 Environmental Performance Monitoring

This activity verifies whether or not goals stated in the EMP are being achieved. To do this, you need some way to measure progress towards your goals. Measures are usually expressed in numbers – tons of waste generated, pounds of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emitted. For example, if your goal is to reduce hazardous waste, then your measure might be the pounds of waste generated over a year's time. A target tells you by how much you want to achieve your goal, as expressed by your chosen measure.

For example, if your goal is to reduce waste and your measure is the amount of waste generated per unit of product, then the target might be to reduce that amount by 10 % within one year. Now you are getting very specific. This is useful to everyone in your company who has to help achieve your company's environmental goals because now they know exactly what they should be shooting for. The Performance Monitoring Worksheet will guide you in identifying meaningful targets.

As your EMP matures, goals and targets need to be revisited. You may choose to keep the same goal but change the target to reflect a higher performance expectation. Or, you may choose to retire certain goals and adapt new ones to reflect new environmental management challenges your business is facing. The idea is that the goals and targets work together to fuel ongoing improvement to the EMP.

4.7.3 Management Review

As the business owner, you want to make sure that the EMP meshes well with your overall business strategy and continues to add value to your business over the long haul. This means that on a regular basis you need to review the goals of the EMP, consider the system of action and accountability it has established throughout your company, and look at the results of monitoring to see how well the EMP is working to achieve compliance and to meet its stated goals.

Also consider how much value the EMP is returning to the business for the effort invested. Are environmental management costs higher or lower than this time last year? Are employees more comfortable with their environmental responsibilities? Is it taking less time overall for your business to meet regulatory requirements? Are you sleeping better at night?

Even if you have been involved in the EMP all along, it is a good idea to set aside some time at least once a year to make sure you are "seeing the forest through the trees." You are probably in the best position to determine when certain procedures, goals, or targets in the EMP have outlived their usefulness and need to be updated or eliminated. Whether or not you want to enlist others in performing the management review is your decision. It may make sense to seek out the opinions of your key supervisors and members of your Environmental Team. However you decide to approach it, you can use the Management Review Worksheets as a guide.

4.7.4 Corrective Action

This is where the rubber meets the road. If you have systems to identify problems but then fail to correct them, you may be worse off than when you started, especially if the problem affects, whether or not, your business is in compliance with applicable laws. Once you have a finding that indicates a problem, you need to do four things:

1. *Investigate the root cause of the problem;*
2. *Create a solution to correct the existing problem as well as preventing the problem from happening again;*
3. *Assign responsibility for corrective and preventive action; and*
4. *Check back later to see if the problem has indeed been solved. The Corrective Action Worksheet will help you work through this process.*

4.8 Compliance Monitoring Worksheet

Step 1

Based on their experience, ask members of the Environmental Team to identify what areas of environmental regulations they believe the business should audit to verify compliance.

Step 2

Decide what criteria to use to prioritize auditing efforts for the coming year. Some criteria you may want to consider:

1. *likely to have a high degree of non-compliance,*
2. *Likely to be the focus of a regulatory inspection in the near future,*
3. *Poses a high potential risk to employees, the community, or the environment, and*
4. *Poses a high degree of liability if not properly managed.*

Step 3

Apply your screening criteria developed in Step 2 to the list of areas to be audited developed in Step 1 to come up with two to three areas to emphasize in audits during the coming year. List them in the table on the next page and indicate for each area whether a full compliance audit is warranted or whether selected areas will be targeted for evaluation.

Step 4

Decide what resources and methods the business can apply to fulfill audit plans identified in Step 3. Some methods to consider:

1. *Assign the responsibility within the business,*
2. *Seek low cost or no cost resources outside your business such as peer exchange with or mentoring from another business that you are not in direct competition with, and*
3. *Hire a consultant. Identify in the table on the next page that will be responsible for each audit.*

Step 5

Identify in the table that follows a target date for completion.

4.8.1 Audit Plan for the Coming Year

Environmental Management Area	Audit Type*	By Whom	By when

Audit Type*

Performance Check: Regular observation of selected activities in the course of daily activities during a given time period by supervisor; manager or other designated person

Targeted compliance audit: An audit of selected compliance points for a major or minor area of environmental regulations

Full compliance audit: A thorough audit covering every applicable compliance point for a major area of environmental regulations

4.8.2 Worksheet for Performance Monitoring

Step 1

For each goal you selected, decide what is the best way to measure progress toward meeting that goal. Helpful hint: to keep it simple, use data that is already available, such as purchasing records, if it can provide any kind of a meaningful measure. This may be better than having employees take time to collect new data, especially in the early stages of the EMP

Step 2

For each goal, decide by how much you want to improve and set a target. Be sure to set realistic targets. Achieving targets in the first year will help employees feel encouraged about their progress and provide momentum for more challenging goals and targets in future years.

Step 3

Assign responsibility for gathering the information needed to confirm whether your company has met its target.

Step 4

Use the table to plan environmental performance monitoring for the coming year.

4.9 Goals and Targets for Mauritian Dodo Hotel

Goal	Targets
Verify compliance with all environmental regulations.	Identify and list applicable regulations by 15/06/09 Develop a system to stay current with new requirements by 31/08/09.
Verify the appropriate management of all waste streams.	Begin monitoring dumpster weekly for wastes that do not belong by 31/5/09 Update employee training on waste management practices by 30/6/09. Create clearly designated and marked areas for patrons to leave acceptable wastes by 1/9/09. Educate patrons on use of site disposal options and unacceptable materials by 30/9/09.
Communicate Environmental Policy to all employees.	Present Environmental Policy to employees and their families at annual picnic, July 2009.
Update Emergency Response Plan.	Finalize written plan, train all employees, and put in place coordination agreements with outside responders by 30/6/09.
Update Emergency Response Plan.	Finalize written plan, train all employees, and put in place coordination agreements with outside responders by 30/6/09

4.9.1 Environmental Performance Monitoring for the Coming Year

Goal	Targets	Responsible for Monitoring

4.9.3 Management Review Worksheet - EMP

Step 1

Has the EMP added value to the business by:

Making environmental compliance more effective? _____ Yes _____ No

Making environmental management less time consuming? _____ Yes _____ No

Causing changes to processes or procedures that reduced liability? _____ Yes _____ No

Causing changes to processes or procedures that saved money? _____ Yes _____ No

How does the EMP detract from the business? What can be done to prevent or reduce this from happening?

Step 2

Based on your responses to the questions in Step 1, what are the three most critical issues that need to be addressed to improve the EMP? If you have critical issues taken care of, what are the three most important?

1. _____

2. _____

3. _____

Step 3

Meet with your Environmental Team and discuss the changes you came up with during Step 2 and why you are suggesting them. Discuss how these changes can best be made, and assign responsibility for following through on making them.

4.9.4 *Corrective Action Worksheet*

Step 1

Describe in one or two sentences the identified problem.

Step 2

Investigate the problem by asking members of the Environmental Team and any employees, who work in the area where the problem is occurring, what they believe the root cause of the problem to be.

Step 3

Determine possible corrective and preventive actions that your business can undertake to respond to the problem. You may want to involve members of the Environmental Team in a brainstorming session to develop a list of possible corrective and preventive actions.

Step 4

From the list of corrective and preventive actions developed in Step 3, decide which one or two will be most effective and feasible given resources available. Write a memo briefly stating the problem, what corrective and preventive actions the business will take, and who will be responsible to take them.

Step 5

Distribute the memo to everyone who needs to know about it. Check in on those who have follow up responsibilities to make sure they understand what needs to be done.

Step 6

Decide how much time should pass before checking to see if the corrective and preventive actions are working. Put a reminder for yourself on your calendar so you don't lose track of this as time goes on.

Step 7

When the time comes, evaluate the results of the corrective and preventive actions and consider whether the EMP needs to be revised to reflect a better approach to this particular issue for the future.

4.10 Summary

If you have read through this Workbook from beginning to end, you can see that the process of developing an Environmental Management Plan can be tackled in a series of manageable steps that are connected by a flow of information and ideas.

Each step illuminates the path ahead, helping your business to make steady progress towards organizing environmental management in a way that adds value to your business and fits with its culture. The process is designed with built in opportunities to review and improve performance so that the EMP itself will better serve your business as time goes on. This way you can start out simple and build confidence with early success. By revisiting the EMP, it remains a vital tool that grows with your business' capabilities and reflects its strategic direction, rather than being just another dust-covered document.

Some last things to keep in mind:

- Take your time. It is better to develop the EMP over a period of several months to a year than to feel that the effort required has detracted from your core business activities.
- Define the boundaries at the beginning of the process and stay within them. For example, will your EMP cover the entire business to start out with or will you focus on key processes?
- Is your initial focus on assuring compliance with applicable laws, or do you have an interest in environmental performance that goes beyond compliance?
- At what stage do you want to share your EMP with people outside of your business? Making these fundamental decisions early on will make the efforts that you and your employees invest more focused and likely to succeed.

Once you have established your EMP, you may want to give some thought to whether it would be beneficial to your business to pursue outside certification as a formal Environmental Management System (EMS) or verification through a recognition program. For example, if one of your major customers is requiring that you have an EMS, or will be doing so in the future; this could be a compelling reason to take your EMP to the next level.

5 Recommendation on EMS Best Practices

The EMS Best Practices has divided the recommendations into six specific domains. For each environmental domain, a checklist has been provided so as to enable the identification of priority and the measures to be taken.

Water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To monitor water consumption and rationalize its use • To save and protect local resource
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To control energy use and monitor its consumption • To save energy and reduce atmospheric pollution
Wastes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To reduce waste at the source and improve waster management • To promote the development of local, ecological and social product flows
Purchasing policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To improve product handling and minimize losses and wastage • To manage and master the hotel's supply lines
Noise, air quality, and landscape integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To limit noise pollution • To improve air quality inside buildings • To reduce the impact on the local landscape

● Identification of priory actions

According to the measures that are suggested in the checklist, you must select the actions that you think are significant for your activities and applicable in your hotel.

Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
Monitoring of the hotel's water consumption <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Install water meters in each department <input type="checkbox"/> Determine monthly water consumption and costs	1	Mr. Ben	1 month
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Identify processes and areas where consumption is high <input type="checkbox"/> Determine the water consumption costs for each department	3	Ms Ousha	1 week

5.1 Water Management and Rationalisation

Self-assessment

- What is the total cost of the hotel's water consumption?
- What is the source of the water used by the hotel?
- What is the hotel's overall water consumption?
- Do you know the water consumption in each department?
- Do you implement water-saving measures in the hotel?

If you cannot answer the above questions, it is important to monitor your hotel's water consumption.

- *Leaking tap - 0.1 litre/h ; 1 m³/year*
- *Dripping tap (occasional drips) - 1.5 litres/h ; 15 m³/year*
- *Minor leak in toilet flush valve - 3 litres/h ; 30 m³/year*
- *Trickling tap - 10 litres/h ; 90 m³/year*
- *Serious leak in toilet flush valve- 30 litres/h ; 250 m³/year*

5.1.1 Water checklist

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE AND UNDERSTAND WATER CONSUMPTION			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p><u>GENERAL</u></p> <p>Monitor the hotel's water consumption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Install water meters in each department ● Determine the monthly water consumption and its cost ● Identify activities and areas that cause high consumption <p>Minimise wastage of water</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Install water-saving devices in the appropriate places (flow regulators, water flow sensors, self-closing taps, low-flush toilets, etc) ● Avoid leaving taps open unnecessarily ● Avoid cleaning with high pressure hoses <p>Eliminate leaks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Regularly maintain plumbing fixtures and piping in order to avoid losses ● Replace defective seals and repair damage to water pipes 			
<p><u>KITCHEN</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adjust the water flow according to the type of cleaning to be done ● Do not let water flow while cleaning or rinsing ● Soak the dirty dishes before placing them in the dishwasher to shorten the pre-wash ● Fill dishwashers to their maximum capacity ● Do not defrost food in water, but leave it to defrost in air 			

Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p><u>LAUNDRY</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sort the laundry according to the degree of soiling, so that only the dirtiest items are washed intensively ● Use the washing machines in "full load" mode in order to limit the number of wash cycles ● Eliminate the prewash (allowing a 25% reduction in water consumption) and use water-saving wash cycles ● If possible, wash towels and linen at the request of guests rather than every day ● Reduce water pollution by using less polluting detergents (phosphate free, whitener-free, etc.) ● Check the laundry room's equipment regularly to avoid leaks ● If possible, recover the rinse water from relatively unsoiled loads for the next cycle's prewash and wash 			
<p><u>ROOM SERVICE, ACCOMODATION</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Install flow regulators on the showerheads in order to decrease consumption from 20 to 12 litres/minute ● Choose water saving toilets that use 6 litres for each flush or with a dual flush mechanism (offering a choice of half- or full-cistern flushes) ● Invite – as far as possible – the guests to reuse the towels and bed-linen (70% of guests readily agree to this) ● Train the staff to respect the instructions concerning the reuse of towels and bed-linen ● Distribute brochures and flyers, or post stickers and posters, inviting guests to save water 			

Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p><u>POOL</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cover the pool outside of the opening hours so that the water does not evaporate or get dirty ● Reduce the use of chlorine in the water and /or choose other treatment systems (ozone, electrolysis, salt, etc.) ● Reuse the pool's water to wash the floor 			
<p><u>GARDENS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Choose plants that are suited to your region's climate and rainfall ● Avoid flower beds that quickly dry up ● Water lawns early in the morning and late at night to limit evaporation ● Install automatic sprinkler systems and localized devices (drip irrigation systems for roots, etc.) ● Lay out slopes so that water infiltrates the ground without causing erosion ● Reuse the water that was used in the kitchen to wash fruits and vegetables for watering the garden ● Collect rainwater for watering the lawns 			

The use of flow regulators on shower heads save 40 litres per 5 minutes shower, which amounts to more than 10 % water consumption per day and per

5.2 Energy Efficiency and Economy

Self-assessment

- What is the total amount spent by the hotel on energy consumption?
- What is the total energy consumption of your hotel?
- Do you know how much energy each department consumes?
- Do you rely on different energy sources, among which are those labelled 'clean'?
- Do you use processes that optimise energy consumption?

If you cannot answer the above questions, it is important for you to get interested in your hotel's energy use

5.2.1 Energy Checklist

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE AND IMPROVE ENERGY CONSUMPTION			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p>GENERAL</p> <p>Monitor regularly energy consumption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check the electricity meters at least once a month ● Install meters in each department to monitor energy consumption ● Monitor hot water consumption as much as possible ● Calculate the energy consumption costs for the hotel and departments ● Determine which areas consume the most energy 			
<p>Improve the lighting system</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Investigate the use of hotel lighting and observe how long the various lights are switched on each day ● Use energy-saving bulbs, especially in high consumption areas (a traditional bulb consumes 60 W, an equivalent energy-saving one 11 W) ● Install timers and movement detectors to reduce lighting time in selected locations (bathrooms, hallways, parking lots, etc.) 			
<p>Reduce energy consumption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Code the light switches (using labels or a colour code) so that you can switch on only those lights that you need ● Reduce general lighting during daytime and make sure that exterior lighting is switched on only at night (you can use photoelectric cells for example) ● Operate machines according to the manufacturers' recommendations for better energy efficiency ● Choose high performance insulation systems to minimise heat losses and gains ● Reduce the number of lifts that are operated during off-peak hours ● Train the staff to do the right things, and invite guests to get involved ● Repair or replace faulty equipment with more efficient and economic alternatives ● Use solar panels to heat water for the guest rooms (saving 40% on the energy costs of the hotel) 			

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE AND IMPROVE ENERGY CONSUMPTION			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p>Minimise energy losses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organise preventive maintenance of the electric network and equipment, including heating and air conditioning equipment ● Install aerators to reduce the demand for hot water ● Check the insulation on hot water pipes to reduce heat losses ● Install double glazed windows ● Shade windows from the sun to limit air conditioning needs (by means of awnings, curtains, blinds, screens, heat reflecting sheets, etc.) ● When renovating, install revolving doors to limit drafts 			
<p>Recover energy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recover the heat generated by the refrigeration units in order to heat the water for guest rooms or the laundry ● Install closed loops to recover and reuse steam 			
<p><u>KITCHEN</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Avoid turning on kitchen equipment without thinking when arriving in the morning (break the habit) ● Think about the temperature of kitchen rooms when installing or relocating refrigerators and freezers (an extra 5°C increase in room temperature results in a 30% increase in energy consumption for a refrigerator) ● Switch off equipment when it is not required (especially after busy periods) ● Do not exceed preheating times ● Use cooking pots whose diameters are compatible with the cookers or burners ● Cover pots as they are cooking (to boil 1 litre of water in a covered pot requires about 25% of the energy needed if the pot is uncovered) ● Invest in high-performance cooking units when replacing equipment ● Open refrigerators and freezers only when necessary ● Defrost refrigerators and clean the door seals monthly 			

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE AND IMPROVE ENERGY CONSUMPTION			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p><u>LAUNDRY</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fill washing machines to their maximum capacity ● Use low temperature washing programmes ● Choose washing machines that offer high spinning speeds in order to limit drying time ● Avoid overloading the dryer and thereby increasing drying time ● Plan your washing so that the dryers are continuously in use, thereby preventing heat loss ● Plan to use the equipment during periods of low consumption (off-peak hours) ● Allow food to cool down before placing it into a refrigerator or freezer ● Install plastic curtains outside refrigerators or freezers to retain cold air ● Regulate water temperature according to kitchen and cleaning needs ● Do not wash dishes under running water (fill the sink instead) Operate dishwashers only when full 			
<p><u>ROOM SERVICE, ACCOMODATION</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Turn off air conditioning and set heating at minimum in unoccupied rooms ● Choose thermostats that allow you to programme maximum and minimum temperatures (and so prevent guests excessively heating or cooling their rooms) ● Make sure the lights are switched off in unoccupied rooms ● Do not leave television sets on standby (a single television set on standby can consume 193 kWh in one year) ● Make sure that the refrigerators (mini-bars) consume less than 1 kWh/ day and that they are switched off in rooms that are unoccupied for three or more consecutive days ● While cleaning, do not air rooms for more than 15-20 minutes in order to avoid wasting energy on heating or cooling ● Install an air conditioning system that automatically switches off when the windows are open ● Clean and change the air conditioner filters regularly 			

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE AND IMPROVE ENERGY CONSUMPTION

Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p><u>ADMINISTRATION</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Avoid leaving computers switched on when taking breaks longer than 30 minutes (on standby, a computer consumes 95 W) ● Switch off equipment when not in use (a copying machine on standby can consume up to 80% of the energy it uses in working mode) ● Use natural light rather than artificial lighting as much as possible ● Rearrange the workplace to make optimal use of natural light ● Avoid leaving doors and windows open to minimise energy consumption for heating or air conditioning ● Switch off the coffee machine after each use (a coffee machine that is left switched on the whole day consumes as much energy as it uses to make 12 cups of coffee) 			
<p><u>POOL</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Retain the pool's heat by covering it with a thermal cover at night ● Keep the water temperature at 24°C (increasing the temperature by two degrees can consume up to 25% more energy) ● Limit the pool lighting that is not necessary for the users' safety ● Make sure that the pool's thermostat is in working order 			

5.3 Waste Resource Recovery

The rapid development of the hotel industry often goes hand-in-hand with a lack of sanitation and waste disposal infrastructure. It is therefore necessary to implement strategies to minimize wastes at source as well as to recycle them. Indeed, hotels produce large quantities of solid and liquid wastes, which end up in the surrounding environment due to inadequate management and handling. The resulting dirty surroundings will also harm the image of the hotel.

● TYPES OF WASTE IN THE HOTEL INDUSTRY

Non-hazardous wastes (NHW)	Components	Source
Common wastes	Food/kitchen waste, used or dirty paper and wrapping, plastic wrapping or bags, composite wrappers	Hotel's different departments
Cardboard	Packaging	Hotel's purchasing and other departments
Paper	Printed documents, brochures, menus, maps, magazines, newspaper	Administration, reception, guest rooms, restaurants
Plastic	Bags, bottles (that did not contain hazardous material), household goods, individual portion wrappers for various products	Kitchen, restaurants, bars, guest rooms, administration
Metal	Tin cans, jar lids, soda cans, food containers, mayonnaise, mustard and tomato purée tubes, aluminium packaging	Kitchen, restaurants, bars, guest rooms
Glass	Bottles, jars, flasks	Kitchen, restaurants, bars, guest rooms
Cloth	Tablecloths, bed-linen, napkins, clothes, rags	Kitchen, restaurants, bars, bathrooms, guest rooms
Wood	Wooden packaging, pallets	Purchasing department
Organic waste	Fruit and vegetable peelings, flowers and plants, branches, leaves, grass	Kitchen, restaurants, bars, guest rooms, gardens

hazardous wastes (NHW)	Source
Frying oil	Kitchen, Restaurants
Mineral oil	Maintenance Service
Paint and solvent residues	Maintenance Service
Flammable material (gas, petrol, etc)	Kitchen, Garden, Maintenance Service
Fertilizers and chemicals (insecticides, fungicides and herbicides)	Garden
Cleaning chemicals	Maintenance Service
Ink cartridges	Administration
Disk and CD Roms	Administration, Guest Rooms
Batteries	Maintenance Service, Administration, Guest Rooms
Cleaning chemicals and solvent used in dry cleaning	Laundry Room
Fluorescent lights, neon tubes and long-life bulbs	Maintenance Service

A typical food portion weighing 300 g yields up to 835 grams of waste material, 780 grams in preparation and 55 grams upon disposal

A single litre of mineral oil can pollute one million litres of water, spreading to a surface area of 2000m².

Occasionally, hotels produce other types of wastes, such as:

- ✓ Bulky waste (furniture – chairs, desks, sofas, etc.)
- ✓ Demolition and/or renovation wastes (concrete, stone, brick, plaster, glass wool, roof tiles, ceramic material, tiling, window glass, treated wood, pipes, etc.)
- ✓ Inert waste (broken china, chipped glasses, etc.)
- ✓ Used electronic, household and office appliances
- ✓ Discarded refrigerating equipment (refrigerators, freezers)

Self-assessment

- How much does the treatment and disposal of your wastes cost?
- Do you know how much waste is generated by your hotel?
- What are the types of wastes generated and their respective volumes?
- How do you dispose of your wastes? What proportion of the hotel's wastes is recycled?

If you cannot answer the above questions, it is necessary to establish a more efficient management of your hotel's wastes.

5.3.1 WASTE CHECKLIST

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE, REUSE AND TO RECYCLE WASTES			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p>GENERAL</p> <p>Examine the major sources of wastes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify the major sources of waste generation in the hotel ● Determine the quantities and the composition of wastes ● Determine the costs of treatment and disposal of wastes for each department ● Check that the practices of the hotel are in compliance with current legislation ● Segregate wastes at source ● Organize at-source segregation of wastes at source (segregating those wastes for which there exist local recycling networks) ● Organize workspaces in such a way as to facilitate waste segregation ● Distinguish containers by means of colours, labels, or symbols (pictograms) for each type of waste ● Instruct employees in the use of the different containers ● Check regularly if the segregation of wastes is being practised. 			
<p>Reduce the total amount of waste</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Order materials according to your needs to minimise waste ● Maintain and repair equipment in preference to replacing it ● Choose sustainable products and use them correctly to increase their life span ● Use refillable products instead of disposable ones ● Limit the use of individually packaged products 			
<p>Make the necessary arrangements for non-recyclable wastes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dispose of non-reusable and non-recyclable wastes using appropriate methods (that comply with existing regulations) ● Keep hazardous wastes separate from non-hazardous wastes in order to avoid contamination and to facilitate handling ● Take the necessary precautions for the disposal of hazardous wastes ● Do not throw away batteries and accumulators with household wastes, but collect them separately 			

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE, REUSE AND TO RECYCLE WASTES			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p>Reduce packaging wastes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Buy materials that have the least packaging ● Rationalise purchases to avoid ordering small quantities ● Give preference to suppliers that take back their packaging ● Investigate the possibility of selling some wastes to recyclers (paper, cardboard, plastic, metals, etc.) 			
<p>Reduce the impact on the environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Find out about possible local means of processing waste to comply with regulations ● Do not burn waste outdoors, do not disperse them in nature or bury them ● Choose the products that are least polluting and most sustainable ● Recycle electric and electronic appliances and donate unwanted appliances that are still working to local associations 			
<p><u>KITCHEN</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check expiration dates of foodstuffs and use food items in the order in which they were purchased – “first-in, first-out” ● Make sure that fresh and perishable products are stored at the appropriate temperatures ● Install containers specific to particular types of waste in the waste storage area to recover packaging and to promote segregation ● Collect biodegradable organic wastes separately in order to compost them or reuse them as animal feed ● Do not discharge oils into sinks or toilets to avoid clogging pipes and disrupting wastewater treatment systems ● Collect used oil and dispose it in an environmentally friendly manner ● Store liquid wastes in adequate containers and dispose them correctly ● Stop using disposable tableware ● Reduce the use of individual portions (e. g. jam and butter) where this can be done without compromising hygiene 			

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE, REUSE AND TO RECYCLE WASTES

Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p><u>LAUNDRY ROOM</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sort textiles according to their degree of soiling and colour to avoid damaging them ● Choose adequate detergents and use recommended dosages ● Avoid leaving detergent in humid places ● Keep clothes hangers and reuse them ● As far as possible, reuse the laundry room's plastic bags or replace them with wicker baskets or cloth bags ● Rather than throwing them away, transform old bed sheets into laundry bags ● Collect chemical containers according to the manufacturer's instructions and send them back to the suppliers after busy periods) ● Do not exceed preheating times 			
<p><u>ROOM SERVICE, ACCOMODATION</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use refillable dispensers for hygiene products (the rate of use for individual portions is often only 30%, and even less in the case of soap) ● Organize segregation in the guest rooms with clear communication to hotel guests and by providing adequate means (baskets, etc.) ● Improve waste collection by adding compartments to room service trolleys for different types of wastes. However; employees must never sort the contents of waste bins) ● Reuse old bedding and napkins as rags 			
<p><u>ADMINISTRATION</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reduce the printing of documents whenever possible and ● use e-mail ● Reuse the blank side of used paper as scrap paper ● Use the two-sided printing option on printers and copying ● machines whenever possible ● Use recycled paper whenever possible ● Collect paper and cardboard wastes separately ● Limit colour printing and copying ● Return toner and ink cartridges of printers and copying machines to suppliers ● Avoid using disposable tableware (plastic cups and mugs) 			

5.4 Purchasing Policy

Purchases made by hotels are linked to the need to satisfy guests' expectations and offer them quality service. Nevertheless, purchased products must be considered in their integral life cycle. Indeed, the different stages of the life of a product – manufacturing, marketing, use and disposal – all have an impact on the environment. The purchasing of “green” products helps to minimize these impacts. These products favour biodegradable, recyclable, non toxic and less processed materials, and their use in the context of a hotel leads to smaller water and energy consumption. Hotels can encourage the use of “green” products by raising the awareness of staff, suppliers and guests. Beyond the ecological aspect, the impact on working conditions must also be factored in when selecting products.

Since 50% of a hotel's solid wastes consist of the packaging and containers of consumed products, it is extremely important to try to reduce their quantity.

The hotel can use eco-labeled products which have a guaranteed limited impact on the environment. In addition to the ecological benefit, these products are economically advantageous. Indeed, while in use, electrical appliances cost 20 to 50% of their purchase price in energy.

Self- assessment

- Do you favour local products whenever possible?
- Do you favour biodegradable, recyclable or reusable products?
- Do you pay attention to processes involved in the preparation of the products?
- Do you purchase appliances and other equipment that are designed for minimum water and energy consumption?
- Are you willing to spend a little more in order to protect the environment?
- Do you ask your suppliers about their practices regarding environment protection and working conditions?

If most of your answers are negative, it is important that you change your purchasing policies.

5.4.1 Purchasing policy checklist

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE, REUSE AND TO RECYCLE WASTES			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p>GENERAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Examine the major sources of wastes ● Buy only what is needed (avoid unnecessary supplies) ● Buy local products to reduce pollution from transportation ● Prefer, whenever possible, products that are recycled, reusable, repairable, biodegradable, recyclable, fair trade and/or eco-labelled. ● Use the hotel's products and equipment in a rational way ● When purchasing new equipment, take their water and energy consumption into consideration ● Prefer products with little packaging and that use single-material packaging (homogenous and polystyrene-free) ● Avoid disposable (one-trip) products ● Identify and choose suppliers that have already implemented eco-efficiency measures and who agree to take back packaging and used material ● Replace paper towel dispensers in wash rooms with energy-saving hot air blowers ● Involve guests in the selection of "green products" ● Rent equipment that is seldom used by the hotel, instead of buying it ● Purchase appropriate mercury- and cadmium-free batteries and rechargeable batteries for applications involving frequent use 			
<p>SHOPS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● If applicable, encourage the shops in the hotel to sell products that are made in ecologically- and socially-friendly ways ● Do not allow shops in the hotel to sell souvenirs made from protected or endangered animal or plant species 			

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE, REUSE AND TO RECYCLE WASTES			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p><u>KITCHEN</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Choose, whenever possible, organic products ● Choose seasonal fruits and vegetables ● Use fresh products with little or no preservatives and food-colouring and with as little packaging as possible ● Purchase in bulk rather than individually packaged items ● Pay attention to the origin of the foodstuffs used ● Equip the kitchen with energy-efficient appliances ● Choose the least polluting cleaning agents 			
<p><u>LAUNDRY</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Equip the laundry room with machines in energy class A (saving at least 23% on energy consumption) and with washing machines having low water consumption ● Buy compact, concentrated products and/or eco-refills to limit packaging wastes ● Avoid using detergents containing bleach (products of chlorine), phosphate, EDTA, NTA (sodium nitriloacetate) ● Dispose of non-reusable and non-recyclable wastes using appropriate methods (that comply with existing regulations) ● Prefer detergents whose components are active at low temperature (30°C) ● Adhere to recommended dosages to avoid unnecessary pollution of water ● Choose dry cleaning products that minimise pollution ● If you work regularly with a dry cleaner; return the clothes hangers and replace the plastic protection covers with paper or cloth covers 			
<p><u>RESTAURANTS, BARS</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Avoid using paper tablecloths and napkins ● Use table linen made with environmentally friendly materials, free of hazardous dyes, heavy metals and formaldehyde ● Choose wash-resistant materials ● Avoid using plastic cups or disposable tableware ● Prefer draft drinks or deposit bottles 			

OBJECTIVE: TO REDUCE, REUSE AND TO RECYCLE WASTES			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<u>ROOM SERVICE, ACCOMMODATION</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prefer furniture which is easily disposable, being mostly recyclable ● Install refillable soap and shampoo dispensers in the rooms to reduce packaging and rationalize their use ● Use recycled toilet paper ● Choose concentrated, environmentally- and health-friendly cleaning agents ● When cleaning, avoid the use of disinfectants 			
<u>ADMINISTRATION</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Buy reusable ink and toner cartridges which can be sent back to the supplier ● Purchase paper with at least 50% recycled fibres, or non-whitened or chlorine-free bleached paper ● Prefer equipment with a low energy consumption, having recycled or recyclable components and long life spans ● Use the "energy saving" functions that switch an appliance into sleeper mode if it is not used for a certain length of time and the "cancel" function to suspend a print job in case of a mistake ● Prefer rechargeable batteries 			
<u>GARDEN</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use organic or biological fertilizers and garden products 			

5.5 Logistics Efficiency Handling and Management

A hotel purchases large quantities of merchandise that require specific handling and storage. When the merchandise is received, a number of steps must be taken in order to guarantee the preservation of its quality. In addition to the location of the storeroom, the human factor is also crucial. Educating employees and raising their awareness are aspects that must be considered. Moreover, making regular inventories of the stock can limit losses and avoid over-consumption.

Self-assessment

- Do you keep your stock records up-to-date?
- Do you have specific procedures regarding the handling and storing of merchandise?
- Do you give information to or educate the staff about correct procedures?
- Do you regularly carry out checks in storage areas?

If most of your answers are negative, it is important that you rethink your logistics procedures.

Better materials handling and storage limits losses. Furthermore, the staff must know and apply safety and hygiene rules when receiving, controlling and storing merchandises.

5.5.1 Logistics Checklist

OBJECTIVE: TO INSPECT THE STOCKS, TO MANAGE AND TO CONTROL			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
Quality of delivered supplies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examine the packaging of the products delivered to you Check that the contents are not damaged Return the damaged materials to the suppliers 			
Storage conditions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organize the storage area systematically Establish storage policies according to instructions provided by suppliers or as mentioned on the labels Check that the packaging is not damaged during storage Prepare a maintenance schedule for the storage areas and warehouses Update regularly the inventory of stored materials Document mishandling or storage problems 			
Storage of chemicals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep all chemical products (especially those that are hazardous) in a designated, protected, and safe area Respect the storage instructions provided by the manufacturers Label containers of hazardous substances clearly Avoid storing substances that could interact in the same area Ensure that the necessary storage conditions are maintained to avoid accidents (appropriate temperature, ventilation, etc.) Avoid exposing flammable products to the sun or to any other source of heat 			

OBJECTIVE: TO INSPECT THE STOCKS, TO MANAGE AND TO CONTROL			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
Optimal supplying <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Avoid excessive purchasing to limit surplus and loss ● Inspect the stocks and keep a record of them (register or database) ● Check expiration dates of materials to avoid having to discard out-of-date and unusable materials ● Train the staff to work according to the principle of "first in, first out" 			
Losses and leakage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Avoid accidents and contamination by using appropriate equipment to handle materials when necessary ● Close lids and taps to reduce leaks and spills 			

5.6 Noise, air quality and landscape integration

Just like any other type of pollution, noise has an impact on the quality of life and on health. Hotels are, above all, meant to be places where one can relax and rest. This often proves difficult because of the noise level. It affects hotel guests and the staff, as well as the hotel's surroundings. Exposure to noise pollution above 60 dBA has an impact on mood, the quality of sleep, and stress levels. It can also give rise to auditory fatigue (buzzing and ringing). Prolonged exposure to high noise levels, above 90 dBA, represents a hazard to hearing (which can result in moderate to severe deafness).

Self-assessment

- Do you know which the noisiest areas in your hotel are in order to limit the noise levels there?
- How many of your employees are exposed to high noise levels?
- Do your guests or neighbours complain about noise pollution?
- Determine here if noise is a problem in your hotel

If guests complain, it may be due to internal noise and lack of acoustic insulation.

5.6.1 Noise checklist

OBJECTIVE: TO PROTECT THE STAFF AND GUESTS FROM NOISE			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
Evaluate risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure the noise levels and record them • Monitor the variations in noise levels in the noisy areas 			
Act on your environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce noise at its source • Install sound insulation and other means of damping vibrations 			

OBJECTIVE: TO PROTECT THE STAFF AND GUESTS FROM NOISE			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
Change your organisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Accept deliveries only at agreed hours ● Relocate noisy machines to an isolated area or away from the hotel and its surroundings 			
Protect your staff <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inform the staff of the long-term health effects linked to noise pollution ● Provide the employees who are exposed to high noise levels with individual ear protection 			
Look after your well-being of your guests' and the quality of the environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Carry out noisy activities at times which will cause the least nuisance for the guests and the surroundings ● Display posters in exposed areas to raise employee awareness 			

5.7 Air Quality

As with all industrial activities, tourism contributes to atmospheric pollution. Hotel boilers emit atmospheric pollutants, such as particles, carbon dioxide (CO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). Emissions from road traffic associated with the hotel also contribute to atmospheric pollution.

Furthermore, indoor air pollution is a typical feature of hotels. Many sources contribute to the deterioration of air quality inside a hotel. Pollutants range from mere bad odours to toxic hazards, and include kitchen smells, sewer emissions, tobacco smoke, allergens (acarids, moulds, etc.), and volatile organic compounds (found in cleaning agents, paint and solvents, glue, varnish, thinner, etc.).

The life span of Chlorofluorocarbons in the atmosphere can exceed 100 years. These chemicals are responsible for the deterioration of the ozone layer.

5.7.1 Air Checklist

OBJECTIVE: TO PROTECT AIR QUALITY AND TO PROTECT STAFF AND GUESTS			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
Allergens <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clean tanks and taps during periods of extended shutdown ● Clean up mouldy areas with bleach and ventilate them in order to diminish humidity ● Avoid dust accumulation by regularly washing bed linen 			
Outdoor air quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check and maintain regularly boilers and cooling equipment ● Change the filters of air conditioning equipment regularly ● Draw up a list of all the cooling equipment (air conditioning, refrigeration), 			
Outdoor air quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● check their airtightness and remove and dispose appropriately of refrigerant fluids (CFC) which are harmful to the ozone layer ● Monitor leaks in refrigerating systems ● Select fire-extinguishers and fire fighting systems that are halon-free (since halons also contribute to the destruction of the ozone layer) ● Ask your suppliers to switch off the engines of their vehicles when delivering supplies 			
Indoor air quality <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide high performance indoor ventilation ● Identify sources of pollution and eliminate them or decrease their effects ● Create non-smoking places in public areas ● Mark smoking and non-smoking rooms clearly, if the hotel is not completely smoke-free ● Limit the use of aerosols and check that they will not damage the ozone layer ● Choose sprays that do not use propellant gases ● Ensure close adherence to the instructions for the use of cleaning agents (e.g. "do not use in a confined space", "do not inhale fumes") ● Prefer products that are solvent-free to avoid emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) ● Choose biodegradable cleaning agents ● Do not mix cleaning agents (interactions between substances can increase their toxicity) 			

5.8 Landscape integration and protection of natural resources

Self-assessment

- Does your hotel's visual appearance fit into its surroundings (in terms of colours, shape, and size) and into the region's cultural landscape?
- Did you employ a landscaper during the development of the hotel?
- Do the building materials contain local natural products?
- Did you employ local craftsmen when building?
- Did you lay out gardens and limit the area that paved or built on?

5.8.1 Landscape integration and protection of natural resources checklist

OBJECTIVE: TO PROTECT AIR QUALITY, AND TO PROTECT STAFF AND GUESTS			
Actions to be taken	Priority (1 to 3)	Name of person responsible	Deadline
<p>Allergens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check if you are in conformity with your region's estate layout policy ● Give heed to environmental recommendations in laying out your hotel ● Aim for visual continuity with the architectural style of the surroundings ● Preserve local identity and the natural heritage ● Whenever possible, use sustainable materials produced locally ● Lay out green areas and gardens to make the site more pleasant (preferably using indigenous plants) ● Place the parking lot in an inconspicuous area of the hotel ● Choose, when needed, mineral materials that have a link with the region's geology 			

6 CONCLUSION

The safe guard of our unique Flora and Fauna is not as thought the business of others but relies on the cumulative and sustained action of each and everyone. Lagoons and marine resources are very much stressed with human activities ranging from the common individual spending some time to relax, fishermen looking for their subsistence and hotels catering for making the holidays of tourists memorable among many other activities. The manual has targeted hotels as the main component for the implementation of best practices for the conservation and preservation of coastal biodiversity and reduced stress on the environment but also offers much relevance to domestic and the professional public at large. It can be used by every one wishing to contribute to the concept of sustainability either in their business activities or immediate surrounding environment.

The application of best management practices in hotels can produce immediate and tangible beneficial results. More importantly, implementation can be spread gradually to cover all activities resulting in reductions in cost and increases in profits. Additionally, this will increase the competitiveness of the hospitality sector responding to tourists, who are becoming more environmentally discerning.

This best practice manual takes into consideration that the development of best management practices should be supported by the development of the related management systems; that is, environmental policy, market-based incentives, appropriate purchasing policies, environmental management/monitoring system, staff training, and assigning the responsibility for the programme to a senior member of staff. By communicating clearly its environmental policies, commitments and program, the goodwill and image of the hotel are enhanced and become long term assets of the company.

The manual offers a walk-through user-friendly guide to the implementation of Environmental Management Best Practices with tips and recommendations that can be readily implemented with no other investment than will power and re-engineered mindset.